

Diagnosis of Septate Uterus: A Multiple Criteria Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The diagnosis of septate uterus remains challenging due to differing criteria across classification systems (ASRM 2016, ESHRE/ESGE 2016, and CUME 2018), leading to inconsistencies and potential overdiagnosis. Despite these classification differences, current evidence does not support an association between septate uterus and infertility. Additionally, hysteroscopic metroplasty, the standard surgical intervention, has not been conclusively proven to improve reproductive outcomes, as seen in the TRUST trial. Given the risks of overdiagnosis and unnecessary surgical interventions, establishing a standardized diagnostic criterion is crucial to ensuring appropriate patient management and avoiding unwarranted procedures.

Keywords: Septate uterus, Uterine septum, Hysteroscopy, Metroplasty, Infertility

1. Introduction

Diagnosing the septate uterus is not easy, as it does not have a single accepted criteria defining it. While the initial American Fertility Society (AFS) 1988 classification used subjective interpretation for diagnosing it, the updated American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) 2016 criteria started using morphometric measurements (Pfeifer et al., 2016) for the first time. The European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology/European Society for Gynaecological Endoscopy (ESHRE/ESGE) 2014 classification, which was again updated in 2016, also discussed morphometric criteria but their criteria were significantly different from ASRM 2016 (Grimbizis et al., 2016). Adding to this complexity, another classification—the Congenital Uterine Malformation by Experts (CUME) classification—was introduced in 2018 (Ludwin et al., 2018).

1.1 Criteria for Diagnosing Septate Uterus by Different Classification Systems

- **ASRM 2016 criteria:** Internal fundal indentation depth ≥ 1.5 cm with an internal indentation angle $< 90^\circ$, and external fundal indentation < 1 cm (Pfeifer et al., 2016).
- **ESHRE/ESGE 2016 criteria:** Internal indentation of more than half of uterine wall thickness, measured above the interostial/intercornual line. The earlier definition considered the anterior and posterior wall thickness mean, but it was revised in the 2016 update (Grimbizis et al., 2016).
- **CUME 2018 criteria:** Developed through expert consensus by analysing 100 coronal images of the uterus. The classification defines a septate uterus as having an external fundal indentation depth < 1 cm and an internal fundal indentation depth ≥ 1 cm (Ludwin et al., 2018).

1.2 Challenges and Controversies

Even within these criteria, inconsistencies exist. The ASRM 2016 classification introduced a "gray zone," where certain cases—such as those with an internal indentation depth < 1 cm and angle $< 90^\circ$, those with an internal indentation depth between 1–1.5 cm, and those with an indentation depth > 1.5 cm but an angle $> 90^\circ$ —are left undefined (Pfeifer et al., 2016).

Before ASRM 2016, the AFS 1988 definition relied on subjective assessment, later modified by Ludwin et al. by incorporating measurements of internal and external indentation (Ludwin et al., 2019). The ASRM 2016 criteria became stricter with the addition of an internal indentation angle $< 90^\circ$, reducing the number of cases classified as septate (Pfeifer et al., 2016).

1.3 Diagnosis paradox of ESHRE/ESGE classification

The ESHRE/ESGE classification, which is based on the thickness of the wall of the uterus above the interostial line, has led to diagnostic paradoxes. Some uteri having greater internal indentation but not exceeding 50% of the uterine wall thickness are classified as normal by ESHRE/ESGE but as septate by ASRM and CUME (Grimbizis et al., 2016). Additionally, ESHRE/ESGE criteria tend to overdiagnose septate uteri, especially in cases with a thinner uterine wall where even minor indentations surpass the 50% threshold (Ludwin et al., 2018).

In 2014, ESHRE/ESGE, the half-wall thickness was defined by calculating the mean of anterior wall thickness and posterior wall thickness in the sagittal plane (median: 6.5 mm). The 2016 revision redefined it as the wall thickness above the interostial line, with a lower median value of 4.3 mm, thereby shifting many uteri previously categorised as normal into the septate category (Grimbizis et al., 2016).

2. Prevalence and Impact on Reproductive Outcomes

A study highlighted the variability in the prevalence of uterine septum depending on the classification system used (Ludwin et al., 2019):

- **ESHRE/ESGE 2016:** 31%
- **ASRM 2016:** 5%
- **CUME 2018:** 12%
- Only **2.7%** of all women could be diagnosed as having uterine septum using all three classification systems.

Regarding reproductive outcomes, studies show no significant difference in infertility rates between women with or without a septate uterus under any classification. However, women diagnosed with a septate uterus by **ASRM 2016 and CUME 2018** criteria had a higher history of previous miscarriages, whereas **ESHRE/ESGE 2016** criteria did not show such an association (Ludwin et al., 2019).

The overdiagnosis by **ESHRE/ESGE 2016** criteria has been questioned, as it does not necessarily improve identification of women at risk for adverse reproductive outcomes. This may result in unnecessary surgical interventions for patients where the septum is not the actual cause of reproductive issues (Ludwin et al., 2019).

3. Surgical Considerations

Hysteroscopic metroplasty is the surgical treatment for septate uterus, but its effectiveness in improving reproductive outcomes remains unproven. A septate uterus, regardless of the diagnostic criteria used, is not linked to infertility. This understanding helps prevent unnecessary surgeries for this indication. Any observed increase in pregnancy rates following hysteroscopic metroplasty may be attributed to other factors, such as tubal flushing or endometrial injury. The only major study on the topic, the **TRUST trial**, found that the difference in pregnancy outcomes between women who underwent surgery and those who did not was not significantly different (Rikken et al., 2021). However, the trial has been widely criticised due to its long duration (20 years), lack of standardised diagnostic criteria for septate uterus, varying surgical expertise among surgeons, and biases such as immortal time bias and selection bias.

4. Conclusion

It is crucial to establish a **single, universally accepted diagnostic criterion** for the septate uterus. This would help accurately assess its impact and its association with outcomes in reproduction and determine whether surgical correction truly benefits patients. Until then, diagnosing and surgically managing septate uterus in cases with infertility or in those with poor pregnancy outcomes must be done cautiously, and unnecessary interventions should be avoided.

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